

D6.4 Report on feedback of the Services and corrective actions

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BoF	Birds of a Feather session
CoP	Community of Practice
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
HEIs	Higher Education Institutions
IG	RDA Interest Group
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
RDA	Research Data Alliance
TAB	RDA Technical Advisory Board
WG	RDA Working Group

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the steps taken to improve the value and the perceived quality of the services provided by the RDA TIGER project.

The deliverable builds on the principles presented in RDA TIGER D6.2 ‘Initial Quality Control Processes’ and presents the concrete steps the project has taken to develop the “lightweight, but efficient methods to follow the applicability and perceived quality of the services provided”. The deliverable also summarises the feedback received after drafting the D6.3 ‘Report on Pilot Demonstrator Groups’ through formal and informal channels. The foundations of the service improvement steps are as follows:

- In-depth service quality gap analysis and modelling, extending on the earlier analysis based on *Services Marketing: People, Technology, and Strategy* by Lovelock and Wirtz;
- Presentation of the quantitative and qualitative feedback collection approach and conclusions that can be drawn from the currently available data;
- Steps taken to improve services during the first half of the project;
- Conclusions and the next steps, including plans for further quality improvement steps

The deliverable mentions relevant developments in the overall RDA landscape (parallel service improvement activities by the RDA foundation and other RDA regions beyond RDA Europe), as some of the changes in the landscape have a potential impact on the customers’ perception of RDA TIGER and its services.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Terminology

We will use the acronym **WG** or “group” to denote an RDA Working Group. For other groups, we may use **IG** as a shorthand for “interest group” and **CoP** for “community of practice”.

As defined in deliverable D2.2¹, the RDA TIGER considers all members of the supported WGs as users of its services. However, the co-chairs are the primary contact points and could thus be seen as being in the customer role (as engaging a service provider – RDA TIGER – to support the users).

While the project’s impact extends considerably beyond the working group co-chairs, the value provided to the broader group stakeholders is either dependent or considerably enhanced by the efficient steering of the working group efforts that RDA TIGER supports. This broader group of stakeholders is described in section 4 of deliverable D2.2.

2.2 Related deliverables

This deliverable is most closely related to the following project deliverables:

- D3.2 – The deliverable provides the latest update on the project’s Landscape analysis and engagement service, including progress to date in engaging and supporting new and existing RDA Working Groups (WGs), and the development of potential future user communities for the landscape and engagement service.
- D4.2 – This documents reports the progress with the WG Output Support services, particularly the RDA Maintenance Platform (RDA-MP), and various output guidance services. The objectives are to ensure high quality, usefulness, maintenance and sustainability of the WG outputs by making it easier to curate, visualise and query information related to WG outputs, authors and their relationships.
- D5.2 - This document looks at the efforts made so far to evaluate the performance of the RDA TIGER facilitation service, proposing updates to the original description, service stages, and tasks and activities. It also assesses the feedback received from those WGs availing of TIGER facilitation support and reflects on the experiences of and lessons learned by the facilitators who have delivered the service to this point in the project.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7991152>, section 3.2

- D6.2 - This deliverable describes what is meant by quality in the RDA TIGER project, the model used to present the service and their targets, the basic quality control mechanisms used in services, and the overall quality control process of the project.
- D6.3 - This is a report on the achievements of the RDA TIGER pilots within the first year of the project. It gives a summary of the work carried out to date to support the pilot groups with the help of the RDA TIGER facilitator, and what services have been launched and employed. Finally it highlights feedback on the different services and lessons learned and ideas for moving on and refining the services.

2.3 Scope of the changes

Service Quality—as experienced and perceived by the users of the RDA TIGER services—is a cross-cutting issue that needs to consider all aspects of the project. This includes internal processes, customer and user contact points, dissemination activities targeting the broader RDA community and the general public, and developments outside the project’s direct sphere of influence.

At this stage, the key focus will be on supporting facilitators in their role as the primary contact point between the users and the RDA TIGER. The facilitators have generally played a key role in introducing the working group co-chairs and group members to the other services – primarily dissemination and landscaping services so far – provided by the RDA TIGER.

The communications service will also be analysed, and potential areas for improvement will be identified. In general, the communications service is a generally well-understood service that is expected to bring groups that are in later stages of their lifecycle into contact with the RDA TIGER. Thus, while in-depth analysis of the communications service is outside the scope of this deliverable, it is included in the user journey analysis.

3 Methodology

3.1 In-depth Service Quality Gap analysis

Based on the model presented in the *“Services Marketing: People, Technology, and Strategy”* by Lovelock and Wirtz², as discussed in deliverable D6.2, there are five potential gaps within the service organisation that can lead to the “final gap”: **service quality gap** (difference between what the customers expect to receive and what their perception of the service actually delivered is).

² Jochen Wirtz and Christopher Lovelock, World Scientific Publishing Company (2021), ISBN: 978-1944659790

Figure 1 Potential Service Gaps as presented in the deliverable D6.2

The following sections present an analysis of the ways and degrees the gaps of the model apply in the case of the RDA TIGER. The definitions of the gaps have been edited for brevity; deliverable D6.3 presents the conceptual background in more detail.

We will also briefly discuss three additional aspects of perceived service quality that are relevant to RDA TIGER: the high level of goodwill that exists between the project and the community it serves, the role of the service recovery paradox in service management and customer satisfaction, and the evolution of customer satisfaction as a function of time (Kano model).

3.1.1 Knowledge Gap

The knowledge gap is the difference between what management (RDA TIGER, in this case) believes customers expect and what customers actually need and expect.

This gap is closed mainly by the project's design. The facilitation and communication services were designed based on the experiences of RDA working group co-chairs; thus, the project's architecture is based on a co-design approach. However, as the services evolve and new user communities without prior exposure to the RDA start to use project's services, this gap might emerge .

3.1.2 Policy Gap

The policy gap is the difference between management's understanding of customers' expectations and the service standards set for service delivery. Reasons for setting standards below customer expectations are usually related to cost and feasibility considerations.

The Policy gap is likely, to some degree, an unavoidable issue with any project attempting to serve a diverse community such as the RDA. Ideally, all the co-chairs of all the RDA Working Groups and Interest Groups would receive basic facilitation support, with an option to access other services based on their needs.

3.1.3 Delivery gap

The delivery gap is the difference between specified service standards and the actual performance of the service.

In the context of the RDA TIGER project, a possible source of potential delivery gap issues are the major community events (RDA plenaries). Most of the supported working groups submit session proposals in these plenary events, usually with RDA TIGER support as part of the facilitation service. As with any major event, arrangements related to the event (be it physical, virtual or hybrid) tend to bring up unanticipated issues that need to be dealt with in real time. The plenary events feature several parallel sessions, which means that facilitating the plenary sessions and their follow-up activities requires support from the whole project staff.

At the moment, customers understand this delivery gap well. However, this area needs careful monitoring, especially during the upcoming hybrid meetings (Costa Rica in 2024 and Brisbane in 2025) that present additional challenges due to the need to operate across challenging time-zone differences.

3.1.4 Communication gap

The difference between what the service provider communicates and what is delivered. The components of this gap are internal and external communications gaps. The internal communication gap can emerge when communications staff operate based on different assumptions of service performance and features than the staff actually delivering the service. The external gap is due to the project overpromising, e.g., in order to increase the visibility of the project and its beneficiaries.

In the initial phases of the project, the RDA TIGER team was relatively small, which reduced the risk of internal and external communication gaps while increasing the risks related to the delivery gap. As the project is entering a new phase, with a more diverse service offering and

growing staff, the internal communication gap needs to be monitored. Risks related to the external communication gap are lower due to the strong community engagement in the design of the project.

3.1.5 Perception gap

The perception gap is the difference between what is actually delivered and what the customer feels they have received (due to customers being unable to judge the service quality accurately).

Risks related to the perception gap are fairly low with the facilitation service. The day-to-day working relationship is closest to a partnership, with a joint list of actions and shared situation awareness. The risks are higher with services provided to the customers indirectly. The facilitators work as interfaces to the communication, landscaping and output services. With these services it is impossible to reach a similar level of shared, in-depth understanding of the intricacies of the service provision. A specific issue with the communications service are its dependencies with external services: the new web platform, working group forums and mailing lists that are being migrated to a new platform.

3.1.6 Service quality gap

The service quality gap is the difference between what customers expect to receive and their perception of the service. It is the aggregate of the above five gaps and will be addressed if all of them are managed in a satisfactory way by the service provider.

As noted in the definition, it is impossible to address the service quality gap directly. However, informal negative feedback is quite often not specific. Feedback along the lines of “We feel something is missing” or “some of the co-chairs were a little bit dissatisfied” are symptoms of a widening quality gap.

However, this non-specificity does not mean that this kind of feedback is useless. Analysing potential root causes, engaging openly and listening to the persons giving the negative feedback will help narrow down the specific areas that require more attention. In addition, open communication about the issues and engagement with the customers will – in and of itself – influence several of the gaps through other mechanisms.

3.1.7 Goodwill, service recovery paradox, and the Kano model

As noted earlier, RDA TIGER can rely on relatively high levels of goodwill from its customers. The project was designed by the same community it serves, and the service providers are members of the same community. While this does not mean the project could afford

complacency³, it means that it is easier to manage potential knowledge and communication gaps.

Open communication (including sharing self-assessment results and identified areas of improvement) will also help the project to benefit from the service recovery paradox⁴. In case the project fails to live up to the expectations of its customers and the RDA community as a whole, a well-executed service recovery process will usually end up increasing customer satisfaction.

However, the project needs to consider that during the project lifetime – and especially in the post-project sustainability/exploitation phase – the provided services will move from “delightful novelties” into “basic needs”, as described by the Kano model below.

³ The backlash due to the loss of trust of the community would be severe.

⁴ McCollough, Michael A., and Sundar G. Bharadwaj. "The Recovery Paradox: An Examination of Customer Satisfaction in Relation to Disconfirmation, Service Quality, and Attribution Based Theories." In *Marketing Theory and Applications*, edited by Chris T. Allen, 119. Chicago: American Marketing Association, 1992.

Figure 1 Kano model illustrating increasing customer expectations as the solutions mature⁵

Thus, the criteria for acceptable service performance need to evolve – especially for services that are perceived as “technical” and “scalable”. Due to the high level of human interaction and involvement needed, adjusting these parameters through mechanical metrics might be harder for facilitation service.

4 Feedback received

4.1 Review feedback

The first periodic review of the project provided the project with a number of specific suggestions and comments. The ones that were related to the service provision and actions taken as a result can be summarised as follows.

⁵ Kano model. (2024, April 5). In *Wikipedia*. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Kano_model

The recommendation that the **“consortium should highlight the RDA TIGER project's contribution and emphasise that it goes further from the existing RDA processes”** is addressed as part of the overall project communication plan with a more prominent web and online presence. While the processes (for example, community and Technical Advisory Board reviews) are the same for all of the working groups, support from the RDA TIGER project will allow the group chairs to concentrate on community engagement and the definition of the group's work plan as they have support with management of the RDA-specific routines.

The communication plan will also improve the project's **“identity (including the visual identity) on the website should be made more structured, user-friendly and simple”**. This will be addressed partly through the overall website update and partly by developing focused material targeting the identified stakeholder groups defined in deliverable D2.2.

The project will also analyse **“costing model for the offered services to prepare for post-project exploitation and take-up”** as part of its sustainability planning. It is likely that these costing models will have differences depending on the project services in question. For example, the output services will have a high up-front cost due to technical adaptations and setup work needed, whereas the facilitation service will have a more even effort distribution

Finally, the **technological choices** will be documented (building on the work reported in the deliverable D4.2). In general, due to the nature of the technical solutions - web-based services based on open-source components – the technical solutions can be adapted to procedural and regulatory requirements. However, technological choices related to service provision – for example, solutions for managing landscape information – will shape the internal processes and communication patterns within the project. The assessments of the risks and opportunities related to these technical choices will be analysed as part of the project's continuous improvement activities.

4.2 Pilot working group experiences

The details of the support approach used with these working groups is presented in the deliverable D6.3. Some of the key lessons learned taken on board with the working groups that followed the pilot working groups noted in the deliverable were:

- Early planning support – facilitators acting as sounding boards when the co-chairs draft the case statements and other documents needed to launch the working group.
- The early drafts of the case statements support the identification of co-chairs, since the initial group launching the project may not have sufficient geographical coverage or could benefit from complementary expertise and experience. Initiating the process

of co-chair engagement as early as possible is important, as the potential co-chairs are often already at capacity.

- Facilitators' role in partner and international engagement is crucial. Again, building the momentum and critical mass behind the group requires that the facilitators are supported by the landscaping and communication services.

For the above reasons, the role of the facilitators and the support they provide (as defined in the deliverables D5.1 and D5.2) need to be clarified already at the initial stage of the engagement with the group and its potential co-chairs.

4.3 Co-chair surveys

The number of supported WGs is growing, possibly exceeding the 30 supported group target by the end of the project (the KPI is discussed in more detail in section 5.1). For this reason, it is important to develop a mechanism to track the co-chair satisfaction in a way that has a lower overhead than the systematic interviews/feedback requests used with the pilot groups (reported in D6.3).

The current practice is that the facilitators regularly remind the group co-chairs and members that a feedback form of the project is available, and all the feedback received is welcome on a rolling basis. The form is a combination of numeric feedback and fields that allow free-form, qualitative feedback to be given. Based on experience, WG co-chairs and members are most likely to provide their feedback upon the completion of major milestones in the groups' lifecycles (TAB review, approval of a RDA Plenary Session Proposal etc.).

At the time of writing this deliverable, 11 responses have been submitted through the form. This represents over 55% response rate from the WGs supported by TIGER, which should be considered quite a good response rate and reduces the potential impact of the selection bias. While there is an option of providing anonymous feedback, only two of the responses were submitted anonymously. All of the respondents (including the anonymous ones) answered "Yes" to the question "Do you think this service is needed?".

When assessing the quality of received services, the **percentage of "Satisfied" or "Very satisfied" was over 90%**, with one of the responses stating that the actual service delivery had not started yet (however, the application process had been very smooth).

The project discussed internally if the co-chair surveys should be complemented with more lightweight approaches (e.g. a simple "happy-medium-unhappy" poll at the end of the meetings). However, even such a simple survey can become a distraction and can adversely affect the relationship between the facilitator and co-chairs. Furthermore, the advantage of

a more in-depth survey form is that it makes it possible to provide more in-depth analysis and suggestions for improvement to accompany the quantitative feedback. Thus, having fewer but considerably “richer” data points was seen as the ideal solution.

4.4 Qualitative input

Deliverable D6.3 summarised the feedback received from the pilot groups. In general, the responses were positive, as noted in section 4.2. The qualitative feedback submitted via the feedback form after drafting of the previous deliverable primarily reinforced the lessons learned reports in D6.3:

- Writing Case Statements and identifying co-chairs are some of the key WG stages that benefit from facilitation, perhaps more than initially expected.
- Partner engagement and consensus-building are also important early stage support stages
- Clarifying the role the facilitator plays is important (neither co-chair nor a secretary)

The additional observations and areas of further analysis based on the qualitative feedback are:

- Dissemination support is relevant also in the earlier stages of the WG lifecycle (support engagement and approaching new stakeholders)
- The application form could be optimised for conciseness and clarity, also in terms of highlighting (and clarifying) opportunities to apply for travel grants and other support beyond facilitation and dissemination. Similarly, case studies or success stories would help to make the TIGER support more understandable and concrete.
- Coordination with other sources of WG support (such as RDA US TIGRUS⁶ programme) is important.

In addition to the feedback received through this channel, discussions during the June 2024 selection committee meeting focused on the need to review and update the application form.

⁶ <https://rdaus.org/rda-us-launches-tigrus-facilitation-program/>

5 Service analysis and continuous improvement steps taken

5.1 Project KPIs

The status of the KPIs defined in the project plan is presented in the table below

KPI no	Aspect	Key performance indicator	Target level	Status June 2024
1	Interest on the RDA TIGER support actions (<i>communication / engagement</i>)	# of applications to RDA TIGER support	30 over the project period	17 (see summery below)
2	RDA TIGER WGs are successfully finished (output created) (<i>facilitation, finalisation</i>)	# of WGs supported which have successfully created their respective	15 Working Groups with successfully finished outputs	0
3	Produced services have high quality according to users (<i>all services, quality control</i>)	% of positive (>7.5/10) rating in user feedback	95% positive rating over all services	90% (if counting the one "N/A") 100% of respondents who had received TIGER services
4	RDA TIGER WG outputs have high level of interest and potential impact (<i>dissemination / WG onboarding</i>)	Average (over outputs) # of unique downloads/views of the outputs/yr during project time	500	Pending website update
5	External service provision has been successful (<i>management</i>)	# of provided travel grants, # of provided 3 rd party grants, # of consultant support provided, # of adoption grants	15, 6, 6, 6 respectively	0 0, 1, 0
6	Landscape follow-up and engagement has provided new members to RDA to participate in the RDA TIGER WGs. (<i>engagement</i>)	# of participants in RDA TIGER WGs, who have not been earlier RDA members	50	Pending website update

In general, the number of applications (KPI#1) does not fully reflect the level of interest expressed informally. As the number of supported WGs grow, we can expect the co-chairs and members of the supported groups to use their networks to increase the awareness of the calls. The numbers of applications received per call are as follows:

- May 2023: 3
- September 2023: 6
- December 2023: 3
- March 2024: 2
- May 2024: 3

We expect that more than 15 WGs (KPI#2) will finish their work before the end of the project. Feedback rating (KPI#3) is above the target level when counting the responses that gave a rating on the expected range. It should be noted that maintaining this level of satisfaction should not be an end in itself: collecting rich, actionable feedback – including constructive criticism – will be more important for the project’s long-term sustainability.

The download statistics (KPI#4) and new RDA members participating in the WGs supported by the project (KPI#6) will be assessed once the statistics of the new web platform can be analysed and the maintenance facility is integrated into the platform. The external services (KPI#5) have proven to be less sought after than expected. Reasons for this will be analysed as part of the project’s self-assessment and continuous improvement activities.

5.2 Clarification of the customer roles

The clarification of the co-chairs’ role as the user community (group membership) representatives is – on the surface – a minor conceptual adjustment. However, it allows the project to streamline the continuous improvement and analysis activities.

While the project’s impact and benefits to the broader stakeholder groups are important, they are best realised by supporting the WG co-chairs and allowing them to focus on their expert roles. The project will interact with the group members but always based on agreement with the group co-chairs.

This definition will also reduce risks related to the knowledge, communication and perception gaps by lowering the number of contact points between the project and its users.

5.3 Customer journey analysis

Based on the analysis of the support activities so far, it has been determined that the facilitators are usually the primary contact points between the group co-chairs and the project. The role of Communication as the first TIGER service to be adopted by established WGs requesting RDA TIGER services towards the end of their lifecycle will possibly emerge as the awareness of the project’s ability to support the finalisation of the WG deliverables grows.

Thus, the focus of the awareness-raising and engagement with potential new customers will focus on making these two services seem relevant to group co-chairs and organisers of the BoF sessions. This focus will make it easier to manage the Knowledge gap between the new project customers and the project.

Internally, the project will analyse the mechanisms the facilitators and communications experts can act as interfaces with the landscape/engagement and output services. Streamlining these interfaces reduces the risks related to delivery and communication gaps.

Specific attention has also been paid to managing situations where the selection committee has turned down a request for RDA TIGER support. Even if the process is well-documented and fully transparent, the (potential) customer will feel dissatisfied. However, in most cases, the rejection of the proposal has not been due to the proposal idea not having merit, but its presentation has lacked sufficient detail to assess the feasibility or impact. Considerable attention is thus paid to ensure that applicants understand that re-submitting a proposal that addresses the weaknesses identified in the review process is encouraged and supported by the project. In the best case, this allows the project to benefit from the Service Recovery Paradox.

5.4 Updating the per-service KPIs

The per-service KPIs that are chosen to monitor the project's progress (to complement the overall project KPIs) are presented below. It should be noted that the period until the end of 2024 is used to establish a baseline for the results for the analysis of the final project year results and trends.

- WP2
 - Idea dissemination period: # Social media views, # unique page views
 - Work period: # of unique page views on WG web page, # of dissemination events (posters, speech, videos, etc.) produced.
 - WG end period: Website visits for the output, # social media views, # participants in targeted (virtual or physical) events.
- Landscape analysis service (WP3)
 - # of new RDA members joining the supported WG
 - # of entries in the landscape service database
- Output support/maintenance service (WP4)
 - # of publications and outputs included in the graph database
 - # of community annotations
- Facilitation service (WP5)
 - Project KPI#2

5.5 Costing approach

As the setup/pilot phase of the project has been concluded, the project plans on using collected statistics (such as average effort expenditure per supported working group/service) as mechanisms to come up with cost estimates. Going forward, data will be collected in such

a way that it will estimate the differences in the per-WG effort, as the staff effort is the primary cost factor influencing the sustainability of the project services. This activity has already begun in response to the review comments, and processes are being put in place to facilitate time-tracking in such a way that costing and effort estimates are as accurate as possible and available by the next reporting period.

The output services (WP3) will require a slightly different cost assessment approach, as the setup/launch of a new branch (or instance) of the output service solution is an integral part of the service. The project has identified exploitation opportunities that would allow testing cost models outside the original development context

In addition to supporting the sustainability planning of the project resources, costing information will help manage many of the service gaps, especially the policy and perception gaps.

5.6 Process improvements

The project will define a more systematic, continuous improvement approach, led by WP6 and presented in the project all-hands meetings as a standard agenda item closely linked to the quality bulletin presented in the meetings.

So far, the following process steps have been made based on the observations and analysis of the project's service delivery:

- Complementing email with an instant messaging platform (a project channel on the RDA Slack instance) as a project internal communication channel. This will reduce the communication latency within the project and help process time-sensitive issues in a way that does not add to the mass of emails that would need to be filtered in order to find information that is relevant beyond the short-term activity.
- The principle of separation of the chair and rapporteur/note taker roles in the meetings. This allows the chair to focus on the content, covering all of the agenda points and ensuring all of the project staff members are consulted.
- Clarifying the links and interfaces between the Landscape analysis database and the output service solution.
- The first service improvement and sustainability planning workshop (face-to-face meeting) for in-depth analysis of the results of the project so far.

6 Conclusions and next steps

The project services are running and are sufficiently well-understood that the quality and efficiency can be systematically improved. The integration of services will be further improved with two goals in mind:

- Increased efficiency: streamlined cross-WP links in service delivery
- Assessing the needs (articulated and unarticulated) of the co-chairs and providing a more seamless experience to the co-chairs using the TIGER services.

In terms of tool support, the project's approach for cross-WP communication will be based on low barriers of entry and minimal "friction" in entering and curating information in the shared information sources. In the RDA environment, the benefits of automated tools to manage project workflows are often offset by the increased complexity when compared to the approach of maintaining a "rolling minutes" type of log of decisions and actions.

However, the tool landscape will be constantly monitored. It is possible that scaling up of the support activities and collaboration with other initiatives will bring opportunities for standardised workflow support. In addition to initiatives such as the RDA US TIGRUS project, EOSC-related developments will be carefully monitored in the second half of the project.

